

Task 4.1A (Subtask 2): The RADx Data Hub Ontology

Technical Report

Owner: Stanford University

Revision History

Date (YYYY-MM-DD)	Version Number	Revision Reviewed / Approved By	Brief Description of Change
Mar 25, 2025	v1	Stanford University team	Initial version
Mar 28, 2025	v2	Stanford University team	Reviewed and approved version

Purpose

This report describes the RADx Data Hub Ontology. This Ontology provides a formally structured vocabulary to describe key concepts within the RADx Data Hub.

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Purpose and Motivation

The RADx Data Hub Ontology provides a formally structured vocabulary to describe key concepts within the RADx Data Hub. The primary purpose of the ontology is to:

1. Document key terms used in the Data Hub

The ontology lists and organizes the main types of entities and relationships that are relevant to the RADx Data Hub. This helps ensure that core terms are recorded in a consistent and reusable way.

2. Clarify the meaning of those terms

Each term is defined to reduce confusion and make its intended meaning clear to both technical and non-technical users. This helps support consistent use across teams and tools.

3. Provide synonyms and alternate labels to support consistent usage

The ontology includes common synonyms or alternative names for terms to account for variation in how different groups of users refer to the same thing. This supports alignment across documentation, user interfaces, and data submission processes.

4. Maintain a glossary of acronyms commonly used in RADx

Frequently used acronyms are included as part of the ontology, linked to their full forms and definitions. This helps reduce ambiguity and supports clearer communication across documentation, interfaces, and stakeholder groups.

This shared vocabulary, that is provided and defined by the ontology, serves as the source of truth for terminology used across metadata records, user interfaces, documentation, and program communications.

Design Principles and Scope

The RADx Data Hub Ontology was designed to reflect and support the specific informational needs of the RADx Data Hub. Development was guided by a set of competency questions. Competency questions are natural language questions that define the kinds of information an ontology should be able to represent and clarify. They help scope an ontology by identifying key concepts, relationships, and terminology relevant to its domain. In the RADx Data Hub Ontology, competency questions were used to ensure the vocabulary described by the ontology addresses real-world informational needs. Thus, the competency questions we devised represent the kinds of enquiries users might pose when navigating the RADx Data Hub Study Explorer, RADx data file metadata, and RADx study metadata. The questions were grouped into thematic categories, which informed the identification and definition of ontology terms.

Programs and Organizations

- What are the four RADx programs?
- What is a DCC?
- How was the RADx Data Hub funded?

Data Files and Documentation

- What kinds of files are in a study?
- What is a transformcopy file?
- What documentation exists for study files?

Variables and Data Elements

- What is a Common Data Element (CDE)?
- How do Common Data Elements relate to variables?
- What are Tier 1 variables?
- What is the RADx Global Code Book?

Terminology and FAIR Principles

- What is FAIR data?
- How is the RADx Data Hub FAIR?

This question-driven approach ensures that the ontology remains grounded in real user needs and helps identify which concepts need clear definitions, relationships, or synonym support.

What the Ontology Is Not Intended to Cover

While the RADx Data Hub Ontology serves an important role in standardizing and clarifying key terminology, it has been developed with a specific scope in mind. As such, there are several areas it intentionally does not address, in order to maintain focus and usability within the RADx context.

The ontology is not designed to serve as a full biomedical ontology or to cover the entirety of clinical, laboratory, or epidemiological domains within the COVID-19 research area. Its focus is limited to concepts that are directly relevant to the structure, organization, and terminology of the RADx Data Hub.

Similarly, the ontology is not intended to model detailed data schemas, workflows, or data processing pipelines. It focuses instead on defining and clarifying terminology—supporting consistent metadata, documentation, and communication, rather than specifying data formats or analytical procedures.

Ontology Term Curation and Definition Development

Following the development of the competency questions, we reviewed the list to determine which questions were in scope for the initial version of the ontology. For each selected question, we identified the key concepts involved—both central terms and directly supporting terms—and compiled these into a curated list. These terms were entered into a structured spreadsheet, where each was assigned a preferred label, a clear Aristotelian-style definition (stating what kind of thing it is and how it is distinguished), and one or more synonyms to support consistent usage across tools, interfaces, and documentation. For each term, we also developed one or more example usage sentences. This process greatly enhanced our understanding of the terms and helped refine the definitions. These examples will be used to support end-user documentation and will form the basis of a searchable glossary.

Ontology Content Summary and Structure

The RADx Data Hub Ontology is organized into several subsets of terms, each representing a distinct conceptual area relevant to the RADx environment. These subsets were informed by an initial set of competency questions and iteratively refined during ontology development.

The current subsets include:

Data Definition Terms This subset includes terminology for describing the nature, structure, and properties of data. It covers structural descriptors like TabularData and VariableData; and classification terms such as HarmonizedData. It also includes terms related to data privacy and governance, including De-identifiedData, LimitedDataSet, and techniques such as Suppression and Generalization. These terms support precise descriptions of data utility, structure, and compliance with data protection policies such as HIPAA Safe Harbor.

Data Element Terms This group defines terms related to variables and standardized data elements, including Variable, CommonDataElement, DerivedDataElement, and classifications such as Tier1 and Tier2. These terms enable precise representation of data collection units and their relationships.

File Terms This subset captures terminology related to data files and documentation artifacts in the RADx Data Hub, including distinctions such as OrigCopyFile, TransformCopyFile, and DocumentationFile. Types of files are typically described and classified by the types of data that they contain.

DCC Related Terms This subset encompasses entities involved in data coordination, including classes for DataCoordinatingCenter (DCC), specifically named DCCs affiliated with RADx programs, and associated organizational roles.

Miscellaneous Terms This subset includes additional terms needed to capture project-wide or explanatory concepts that do not fall into the other groupings. Examples include FAIRData, DataAccessRequest, and acronym expansions such as CDCC and DDE.

The vast majority of terms in the ontology are modeled as OWL classes, with a handful of terms being modeled as OWL individuals. All terms are annotated using

standard SKOS and RDFS vocabulary elements. Each term includes a preferred label (`rdfs:label`), a formal Aristotelian-style definition (`skos:definition`), and, where applicable, one or more synonyms (`skos:altLabel`).

Implementation and Maintenance

The RADx Data Hub Ontology is implemented using the Web Ontology Language (OWL 2, <https://www.w3.org/TR/owl2-overview/>) and follows standard practices for ontology engineering. Ontology term definitions are maintained in tabular format and transformed into OWL using ROBOT (<https://robot.obolibrary.org/>) templates. The resulting ontology files are stored under version control using Git, ensuring full traceability of changes and facilitating collaborative development.

Entity type	Term	Print name	Parents	Definition	Example usage	Synonyms	Acronyms
Class	de-identified data		de-identifi...	process to remove or obscure all direct and indirect identifiers that could reasonably be used to identify an individual, thereby reducing the risk of re-identification.	RADx Data Hub, ensuring that all participant names, medical record numbers, and contact information were removed or transformed according to approved de-identification protocols.	De-identified Dataset Non-Identifiable Data	
Class	pseudonymized data		de-identifi...	Pseudonymized data is data that has undergone a data de-identification process in which direct identifiers have been replaced with pseudonyms (artificial identifiers such as random codes), while a separate, secure key is retained that allows re-linking the pseudonyms to the original identifiers under controlled conditions.	Prior to sharing the dataset with external collaborators, the research team applied pseudonymization by replacing participant names with randomly assigned study IDs, while keeping a secure key file linking the IDs back to the participants' identities.	Coded Data Key-Coded Data Indirectly Identifiable Data	
Class	anonymized data		de-identifi...	Anonymized data is data that has undergone a data de-identification process in which all direct and indirect identifiers have been permanently removed, generalized, or transformed such that the data can no longer be linked to the original individuals by any reasonably available means.	Before publicly releasing the environmental health study data, the team applied anonymization, ensuring that no participant could be identified directly or indirectly from the data.	Fully De-identified Data Irreversibly De-identified Data Non-identifiable Data	
Class	generalized data		de-identifi...	Generalized data is data that has undergone a data de-identification process in which specific values have been replaced by broader, less precise categories or ranges, reducing the level of detail to lower the risk of re-identification.	In order to reduce re-identification risk, the research team applied generalization to participant birth dates, replacing exact dates (e.g., 1975-06-23) with birth years (e.g., 1975).	Data with Reduced Precision	
Class	suppressed data		de-identifi...	Suppressed data are data that have undergone a data de-identification process in which specific values, fields, or entire records have been intentionally removed or masked to reduce the risk of re-identification or to comply with privacy, confidentiality, or statistical disclosure requirements.	To protect participant privacy, ZIP codes for geographic areas with fewer than 20,000 residents were treated as suppressed data, with the values removed from the dataset before submission to the RADx Data Hub.	Redacted Data	
Class	zip code truncated data		de-identifi...	ZIP code truncated data are generalized data that have undergone a data de-identification process in which the full ZIP code has been shortened to the first three digits, reducing geographic precision to lower the risk of re-identification.	To comply with HIPAA Safe Harbor requirements, the study team provided ZIP code truncated data, removing the last two digits and retaining only the first three digits of each ZIP code.	Truncated ZIP Data 3-Digit ZIP Data Geographic Precision-Reduced	
Class	age capped data		de-identifi...	Age-capped data are data that have undergone a data de-identification process in which ages exceeding a specified threshold are replaced with a maximum allowable age category, reducing the risk of re-identification for older individuals.	As part of the de-identification process, the research team provided age-capped data by recording all participants over the age of 89 as "90 or older" to comply with HIPAA Safe Harbor requirements.	Top-Coded Age Data Maximum Age Data Upper Limit Age Data	

Figure 1 – An example of one of the spreadsheets that is used to maintain the ontology. Terms, parents, definitions, examples, synonyms etc. are maintained in easy to edit spreadsheets that are compiled into the end ontology.

Ontology releases are generated using the Ontology Development Kit (ODK, <https://github.com/INCATools/ontology-development-kit>), which supports automated validation, quality control, and release packaging. Each term is assigned a persistent IRI and includes metadata annotations following SKOS

(<https://www.w3.org/TR/skos-reference/>) and RDFS (<https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf11-schema/>) conventions. The ontology is periodically updated in response to evolving project needs, feedback from stakeholders, and additions to the RADx Data Hub metadata model.

Governance of the ontology is aligned with the RADx Ontology SOP, and future term proposals, revisions, and structural updates are reviewed by a designated ontology curation team.

Availability

The RADx Data Hub Ontology has been published in BioPortal with an ontology acronym of DATAHUB. It can be viewed and downloaded from BioPortal at:

<https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/DATAHUB>

The screenshot displays the BioPortal interface for the RADx Data Hub Ontology. The top navigation bar includes the BioPortal logo, menu items (Ontologies, Search, Annotator, Recommender, Mappings), and user information (mhorridge, Support). The main header shows the ontology name 'RADx Data Hub Ontology' and its last upload date 'March 25, 2025'. Below the header, there are tabs for 'Summary', 'Classes', 'Properties', 'Notes', 'Mappings', and 'Widgets', with 'Classes' selected. A 'Jump to:' search box is present. On the left, a tree view of classes is shown, with 'radx meta file' highlighted. The right pane shows the 'Details' for the selected class, including its ID, preferred name, definition, and type. Below this, an 'All Properties' section lists 'definition', 'label', and 'prefLabel' with their corresponding values.

Property	Value
Id	http://w3id.org/radx/DATAHUB_00000013
Preferred Name	radx meta file
Definitions	A RADx META file is a metadata file that is formatted in JSON-LD and provides structured descriptions of the attributes and contents of a RADx data file.
Type	http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#Class

Property	Value
definition	A RADx META file is a metadata file that is formatted in JSON-LD and provides structured descriptions of the attributes and contents of a RADx data file.
label	radx meta file
prefLabel	radx meta file

Figure 2 – The RADx Data Hub Ontology is published in BioPortal. Information about the ontology and the classes can be browsed using the BioPortal User Interface.

Conclusions and Future Work

The RADx Data Hub Ontology provides a structured and formally defined vocabulary that supports consistent and unambiguous use of terminology across the RADx ecosystem. Its role as a shared source of truth for concept definitions, synonyms, and metadata labels contributes to improved clarity, interoperability, and alignment across documentation, data submissions, and software tools.

Future development efforts will focus on expanding the scope of terms to accommodate new use cases, enhancing semantic relationships between terms, and improving integration with external ontologies where appropriate. Continued engagement with project stakeholders and metadata users will help ensure the ontology remains practical, usable, and aligned with the needs of the RADx community.

While the ontology was developed specifically for the RADx Data Hub, its design reflects common challenges faced by many data-centric biomedical initiatives. The ontology models a broad range of concepts related to data harmonization, de-identification, metadata description, and FAIR data practices—making it a potentially valuable resource for other data hubs and research projects with similar goals. By building on widely accepted standards and emphasizing generalizable patterns, the ontology lays a foundation that could be extended or adapted to support other scientific domains and collaborative data environments beyond the RADx Data Hub.

Resources

- RADx Data Hub Ontology GitHub Repository
<https://github.com/bmir-radx/radx-datahub-ontology>
- RADx Data Hub Ontology in BioPortal
<https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/DATAHUB>